

A

B

Supplementary figure 1. *S. aureus* status of the EDC samples for the six European farms in time, where panel A represents the three Dutch farms (A-C), and panel B represents the three Irish farms (1-3). Each row represents an individual litter (and in the case of the IRL data the room after week 4 (see first paragraph results)) and each column the relative timepoint (in weeks) of the sample. Orange squares indicate that the sample was positive for either *femA* or *CO1*, blue squares indicate that the sample was negative for both targets. Asterisks in the cells represent *mecA* positivity for the sample. White values mean that the sample was missing or lost due to technical issues.